

How to overcome fatal error issue in esp32-esp8266

One of the common uploading error in esp32 series is fatal error issue . because of that many programmers are do not like to work with them. Let us discuss the reason for this error message and ways to overcome the error.

Am I getting a fatal error ?


```
Connecting..... An error occur
-
A fatal error occurred: Failed to connect to ESP32: Invalid head of packet (0x1B)
```

Figure 1 example of fatal error

Fatal error can be easily recognized , in your Arduino IDE screen there will be an error message that saying, “fatal error occurred” **(figure 01)**. This happen when you try to upload a new code to your esp32 or esp8266.

Why are you getting this error ?

there can be a few reasons for appearing fatal error message on your Arduino IDE .

some of them are.

- **Your board is not in the flashing mode ,**
- **RX and Tx pins are not correctly connected.**
- **Power is not enough for uploading.**
- **Jumper wire issues**

How to overcome these issues ?

Your board is not in the flashing mode ,

1. Press boot (reset) button in your board after connecting to your computer.
2. Now press the upload button in your Arduino IDE interface.
3. Hold your finger in boot button till you see the connecting message in your Arduino IDE.
4. If its works count down must start with percentage values
5. After it reach to 100% you will see done uploading message in your screen .

Some suggest that, instead of pressing the REST button ,

To make your ESP32 board go into uploading mode automatically, you can connect a **10 uF** electrolytic capacitor between the **EN** pin and **GND** . Before doing that please check it by connecting on a breadboard. But I am not suggesting doing that thing . because if the soldering is done by a beginner level person. Board can be damage due to the high temperature cause by the soldering iron , as well as all the pins are verry small compared to the UNO board so the pins can be short .

RX and Tx pins are not correctly connected,

This happens commonly in ESP32 camera model . because it does not have a connecting port to upload a code . To upload a new code to the board we must use an Arduino uno board (figure 02) or FTDI programmer.(figure 03)

Figure 2 program using uno.

Figure 3 program using FTDI.

- **U0R** must be connected to **RX** pin and **U0T** must be connected to **TX** pin.

Power is not enough for uploading.

When we are supplying power to the ESP board first, we can supply **3.3V** by connecting **3.3V** uno pin to **3.3V** ESP32 pin. then we can increase the voltage up to **5V** by connecting just like in figure 2 and figure 3. And remember ESP32 draw some considerable current as well. You can check your power state by pressing the **REST** button as well, then the build in flashlight will be turned on. By observing the brightness of the flashlight, you can get a rough idea about power consumption.

Jumper wire issues.

This can be a reason to many errors and issues not only in esp32 series but also in every electrical and electronic applications as well. Specially check the RX and TX connected jumper wires.